

Farming systems

Raising grass carp with deepwater rice

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We experimented with raising grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella* Val) along with deepwater rice NC492 at two sites during 1988 wet season. Rice seedlings were transplanted 4 Jul 1988 at Girirchalk (Midnapore district) and 20 Jul 1988 at Gosaba (South 24-Parganas district). Fish fingerlings were stocked 1 mo later; average length and weight at stocking were 8.0 cm and 12.1 g at Girirchalk and 10 cm and 18.4 g at Gosaba. No fish feed and no

Production of rice and fish under integrated deepwater rice + grass carp culture trial. West Bengal, India, 1988 wet season.

Experimental site	Experimental plot								Recovery (%)	Fish yield (kg/ha)
	Control -only deepwater rice (yield in t/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)	Fish stocked (1 fish/m ²)	Stocking		At harvest				
				Length (cm)	Wt (g)	Length (cm)	Wt (g)			
Girirchalk (Midnapore)	1.5	1.8	600	8.0	12.1	15.2	80.0	54.0	432.0	
Gosaba (24 Parganas S.)	1.8	1.9	320	10.0	18.4	19.2	96.5	60.0	575.8	

fertilizer was applied.

Rice stand count (recorded from a 0.5- × 0.5-m wooden frame) and general field observations were taken periodically. The fish culture period was 120 ± 10 d.

Rice yield data were taken by standard crop-cut method, adjusted to 14% moisture. Fish growth was measured and yield computed.

Stem density did not differ in plots with grass carp and those without fish. Submersed aquatic weed density appeared to be less in plots with fish. Production of rice and grass carp are summarized in the table.

The results indicate that grass carp may be incorporated into a deepwater rice - fish system without jeopardizing rice cultivation. □

Farm machinery

A hand-operated rice huller

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A hand-operated rice huller has been developed that is inexpensive, simple to construct, and easy to maintain. Its two main components are a commercial hand mill and a conversion kit to replace the stationary disk with a gum rubber disk (see figure). When the abrasive rotating disk is turned, rice grains are pressed against the rubber disk and rolled out. The soft rubber disk removes the hulls with minimal damage to the kernels. The huller can also be used for millet and spelt wheat.

The mill will hull 12 kg short grain rice/h. □

Hand-operated rice huller can process 12 kg rice/h.

Postharvest technology

Aflatoxins in stored rice

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Mycotoxin contamination of agricultural commodities and the consequent health hazards are problems of considerable relevance in tropical countries. Aflatoxins are the most potent hepatotoxic and carcinogenic agents. In staples such as rice, aflatoxins are of great significance to human health.

Rice can become contaminated with aflatoxin under high moisture conditions that may occur with improper storage, insect infestation, or high humidity.

Studies in India indicate that, under normal circumstances, aflatoxin contamination of rice is low (Table 1). However, rice exposed to stress conditions (such as heavy rains) can become highly susceptible to fungal invasion and increased aflatoxin contamination. In rice damaged by

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific understanding.

Table 1. Occurrence of aflatoxin in rough rice and processed rice in India.

Commodity	State	Year	Samples analyzed (no.)	Positive for aflatoxin (no.)	Aflatoxin concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
Rough rice	Andhra Pradesh	1975	272	Nil	-
Rough rice ^a	Andhra Pradesh	1976	80	10	Trace-430
Rough rice ^a	Andhra Pradesh	1977	81	19	30-1130
Rice, raw	Karnataka	1974	35	0	-
Rice, raw	Karnataka	1981	76	4	Trace-120
	Uttar Pradesh				
	Andhra Pradesh				
Rice, raw	Andhra Pradesh	1983	63	0	-
Rice, raw	Andhra Pradesh	1987	64	0	-
Parboiled rice	Karnataka	1974	25	8	0-50
Parboiled rice	Tamil Nadu	1976	18	7	30-130
	Thanjavur				
Parboiled rice	Andhra Pradesh	1981	77	7	Trace-120
Parboiled rice	Andhra Pradesh	1988	22	3	Trace- 10

^aAffected by cyclones.

cyclones along the coastal region of Andhra Pradesh in 1976, 12.5% of 80 samples were positive for aflatoxin; 8.7% had levels from 0.08 to 0.43 ppm. The dominant mycoflora was *Aspergillus flavus*. In 1977, higher aflatoxin levels were found in cyclone-damaged rice: in 81 samples, 23.5% were positive for aflatoxin with 0.03-1.13 ppm levels.

Aflatoxin contamination can be even higher in parboiled rice. Levels

reported ranged from traces to 0.13 ppm.

In studies on the effect of processing, dehusking removed 50-70% of the toxin. Polishing further reduced toxin content to 20-35%. Parboiling reduced toxin content in already infected rice by 50%; dehusking and polishing reduced toxins 7 and 17% more (Table 2).

Rice is a dietary staple in many Asian countries, and consumption of mold-damaged or contaminated rice

Table 2. Aflatoxin content of rough and raw rice after processing.

Treatment	Aflatoxin content (ppm)		
	Masuri	Jaya	Sona
Infected rough rice	53.5	16.2	13.3
Infected rough rice after dehusking	24.0	7.6	4.4
Infected rough rice after dehusking and polishing (10%)	18.8	5.7	2.6
Infected rough rice after parboiling	17.9	9.2	8.1
Infected rough rice after parboiling and dehusking	10.4	5.0	3.1
Infected rough rice after parboiling, dehusking, and polishing	3.5	4.5	2.1

can present serious hazards to public health. Drying to safe moisture levels before storage is an important step. ' In natural disaster situations, the need to monitor stored rice for aflatoxins increases; parboiled rice should be monitored even under normal conditions. □

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACT

Production

Constraints to adoption of rice technology in West Bengal, India

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We studied five villages in Burdwan district under the Operational Research Project on Rice, to identify constraints to adoption of high-yielding wet season rice varieties. The project area has 2,543.76 cultivated ha and is within the irrigation command of

Damodar canal system. Of 3,022 farmers, only 1,073 actually have direct control over agricultural activities.

We used stratified random sampling to select 270 working farmers for the study.

Constraints identified were the following:

Holdings in general were small, segmented, and scattered in different locations in more than one village. Much labor is wasted in the movement of inputs, implements, and produce. Farmers have difficulty supervising all their plots efficiently. Consequently, average yield and net return are low (Table 1).

Irrigation water provided by the Damodar canal system cannot be regulated to fit the varying water

Table 1. Plots owned by rice farmers in Burdwan, West Bengal, India, 1982.

Plots (no.)/ farmer	Yield (t/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Return (\$/ha)
1-3	3.1	271.5	128.0
4-6	3.0	283.3	100.0
7-9	2.9	288.3	93.0
10-12	2.8	291.6	73.3
13-15	2.8	303.3	63.3
>15	2.7	308.2	52.1

requirements of transplanted wet season rice at different growth stages. Minimum flow through the existing water canal is 5 ft³/s, a supply that often is detrimental to the crop.

Puffed rice is an essential component of daily life for the people of this area. Puffed rice prepared from traditional varieties, such as Daharna-